

FACTORS AFFECTING ENGLISH LISTENING COMPREHENSION: PERCEPTIONS OF ENGLISH-MAJOR STUDENTS AT HUFU

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ABSTRACT

Listening skill, especially listening comprehension, plays an important role in the process of learning a foreign language in general, and English language learning in particular. The research associated with learning and teaching English listening skills has been of increasing interest in Vietnam recently. However, research with respect to factors affecting English listening comprehension of English-major students at HUFU is still limited. Therefore, this study is conducted with the aims to investigate listening comprehension problems encountered by first-year English major students at HUFU. Questionnaires and focus-group interviews are used as main instruments to collect data. Based on the findings, the study proposes some recommendations for teachers and students to help students develop more effective learning strategies and eventually improve their English listening comprehension.

Key words: Listening skills, listening comprehension, listening problems

1 INTRODUCTION

It is undeniable that listening is a vital skill in the mastery of any language. According to Nunan (1998), listening is the basic skill in language learning and without listening skill, learners will never learn to communicate effectively. In fact, more than 50% of the time students spend functioning in a foreign language should be devoted in listening. The same claim is supported by Hamouda (2013) who confirms that listening is a fundamental language skill in foreign language because the key to acquire a language is to receive understandable language input. Without understanding inputs at a right level, any kind of learning cannot occur. Rost (2002) also indicates that developing listening proficiency is the key to achieving proficiency in speaking.

However, in spite of its importance in foreign language learning, the teaching of listening skill in general and listening comprehension in particular has long been rather neglected and remained as a poorly taught aspect of English in many EFL programs (Mendelson & Rubin, 1994). In fact, listening comprehension is still one of the least understood processes and EFL learners often regard listening as the most difficult language skill to acquire and have serious problems in English listening comprehension.

From her observation and experience of teaching EFL listening skills, the researcher has found that most of the students studying at the Faculty of Foreign Languages at HUFU, especially freshmen, face a lot of difficulties in listening comprehension. In comparison with other language

skills, listening is considered the most challenging one. In order to identify the perceptions of the students of the role of listening skill as well as of the problems the students have to deal with in their learning English listening comprehension at HUFU, the researcher has decided to conduct the study entitled “**Factors affecting English listening comprehension: perceptions of first-year English major students at HUFU**”. This study aims to address the following research questions:

What is the first-year English major students’ perception of studying listening comprehension?

What factors affect listening comprehension as perceived by the first-year English major students at HUFU?

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Listening comprehension

The term “listening comprehension” has been defined by different authors. Howatt and Dakin (1974) define listening as the ability to identify and understand what others say. This includes the ability to understand the speaker's accent, pronunciation, grammar and vocabulary, and understand his/her meaning. They also state that a good listener is capable of doing these four things simultaneously.

According to Brown and Yule (1983), listening comprehension means a person understands what he/she has heard at normal speed. If he/she learns the text through hearing it, he/she will understand it. Dirven and Oakeshott-Taylor (1984) match listening comprehension with terms such as speech understanding, spoken language understanding, speech recognition, and speech perception. Similarly, Mendelson (1994) points out that listening comprehension is a process where listeners are able to decipher the speakers’ intention, process linguistic forms like the fast rate of speech and fillers, cope with listening in an interaction, understand the message of the text without every single word, and realize different genres.

Anderson and Lynch (1998) argue that listening comprehension is not merely dependent on the speaker, but the listener must play a vital part in understanding what is spoken in front of him/her. They indicate that listeners need to use their previous knowledge and relate it to the new knowledge in order to comprehend what is spoken. Sharing the same view with Anderson and Lynch, Richard et al. (2000) claim that listening comprehension is the process of understanding speech in a second or foreign language, which includes not only the understanding of individual linguistic units (e.g. phonemes, words, grammatical structures) but also the listener’s expectations, the situation and context, background knowledge and the topic. Likewise, Hamouda (2013) states that listening comprehension is an interactive process in which listeners are involved in constructing meaning. Listeners comprehend the oral output through sound discrimination, previous knowledge, grammatical structures, stress and intonation, and the other linguistic or non-linguistic clues. According to Nadig (2013), listening comprehension includes the various processes of understanding and making sense of spoken language. These involve knowing speech sounds, comprehending the meaning of individual words, and understanding the syntax of sentences.

In short, different researchers have different views about listening comprehension, but their definitions of listening comprehension have some things in common. It is clearly that listening comprehension is a complex process in which listeners have a crucial role by activating various types of knowledge such as culture, vocabulary and structure of sentences, and by applying what they know to what they hear, and trying to get the message of the talk.

2.2 The significance of listening comprehension

Language learning depends on listening since it provides the aural input that serves as the basis for language acquisition and enables learners to interact in spoken communication.

Listening is the first language mode that children acquire. It provides the foundation for all aspects of language and cognitive development, and it plays a life-long role in the processes of communication. A study by Wilt (1950) finds that people listen 45% of the time they spend communicating.

According to Coakley & Wolvin (1997), listening is the fundamental language skill which is central to the lives of students throughout all levels of educational development. Listening is the medium through which people gain a large portion of their education, their information, their understanding of the world and of human affairs, their ideals, sense of values, and their appreciation. In this day of mass communication, it is of vital importance that students are taught to listen effectively and critically.

According to second language acquisition theory, language input is the most essential condition of language acquisition. As an input skill, listening plays a crucial role in students' language development. Krashen (1985) argues that people acquire language by understanding the linguistic information they hear. In other words, language acquisition is achieved mainly through receiving understandable input and listening ability is the critical component in achieving understandable language input.

According to Oxford (1990), reading, listening, speaking and writing are four major skills in English study which are closely connected and interact with each other. It is impossible to communicate if you do not listen well and people seldom write well without reading. Very often a language user involves in using a combination of skills. Our ultimate aim is to foster the students' ability to communicate. If their listening is poor, it will have a negative effect on the fulfillment of the other requirements for reading, speaking and writing. Therefore, it is important for teachers to help students to improve their listening skill.

In brief, listening plays an important role in foreign language learning due to the fact that it is used as a primary medium of learning at all stages of language learning. Moreover, listening not only helps learners to understand what people are saying to them but also helps them to speak clearly to others.

2.3 Listening comprehension problems

There have been a significant number of research papers that have been conducted in different countries related to the factors affecting listening comprehension.

Boyle (1984) classifies the factors influencing EFL listening comprehension in three categories based on a survey of EFL teachers and learners in China. The first category is speaker factors which include the linguistic ability of the speaker, the quality of the speech signals, the personality of the speaker and the rate of speech. The second category is related to the oral text including the complexity of lexis and syntax, the degree of cohesion, etc. The third one is related to the listener, such as memory, motivation, background knowledge, experience in listening to the target language and so on. Faerch and Kasper (1986) also identify three internal factors in second language listeners' comprehension, which are quite similar to Boyle's (1984) description of learner factor; they are learner's knowledge of the L2 linguistic code, the degree of socio-cultural competence, and the strategic competence such as learners' ability to guess what speakers meant from the context. Similarly, Teng (2002) identifies four listening factors: listener factor, speaker factor, stimulus factor and context factor. She indicates that "EFL proficiency" is the most important listener factor for EFL listening problems. It implies that student's difficulty may arise from their deficient linguistic knowledge. However, Goh (2000) states that the most common problem is "quickly forget what is heard".

Underwood (1989) states that there are seven factors affecting listening comprehension among EFL learners. First, listeners cannot control the speed of delivery. Second, listeners cannot always have words repeated. Third, listeners have limited vocabulary. Fourth, listeners may fail to recognize the signals which indicate the speaker is moving from one point to another. Fifth, listeners may lack contextual knowledge. Nonverbal clues such as facial expressions, nods or tones of voices can be easily misinterpreted by listeners from different cultures. Sixth, it can be difficult for listeners to concentrate in a foreign language; even the shortest break in attention can seriously impair comprehension. Lastly, students may have established certain learning habits such as a wish to understand every word, which may make them worried if they fail to understand a particular word or phrase.

After reviewing over 130 studies, Rubin (1994) synthesizes the existing research on factors influencing listening comprehension and identifies five major factors that researchers believe to be the most influential in listening comprehension: 1) text characteristics such as speech rate, pause phenomena and hesitation, level of perception, stress and rhythmic patterning perception, L1/L2 difference, syntactic modifications, redundancy, morphological complexity, word order, discourse markers, and visual support for texts; 2) interlocutor characteristics such as gender and language proficiency; 3) task characteristics such as task type; 4) listener characteristics such as language proficiency level, memory, attention, affect, age, gender, learning disability in L1, and background knowledge; and 5) process characteristics such as top-down, bottom-up, and parallel processing, listening strategies, and negotiation of comprehensible input.

Hamouda (2013) studies Saudi students' problems in listening comprehension and finds out seven factors, some of which are similar to Underwood (1989). Besides, he indicates that unclear pronunciation, inability to apply listening strategies, poor knowledge of grammar, lack of

familiarity with the topic, and the length and difficulty of listening materials are among the factors that hinder listening comprehension most.

In Vietnam, several researchers have also found out the listening comprehension problems that EFL learners have to deal with. Quyen and Dan (2018) investigate first-year English major students at some universities in Mekong Delta and they state that students have to face lots of difficulties while learning listening comprehension. These main problems are related to listening materials, linguistic features, listening process, speakers, listeners, psychological characteristics and lack of concentration. They also claim that unfamiliar vocabularies, pronunciation and accent of speakers, the effect of tape recorder, lack of concentration and lack of practice are main causes of the problems.

In conclusion, different authors have identified different factors affecting listening comprehension; however, a large number of researchers indicate that most of listening comprehension problems are related to the listening materials, the linguistic features, the speaker from the listening material, the listener, the psychological characteristics and the concentration of the listener.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Subjects

The participants of this study are 150 English major students who attended the school-year 2017-2018 at Faculty of Foreign Languages at Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry. The study was conducted at the end of the second semester after the students had finished two listening skills courses entitled “Listening 1” and “Listening 2”.

For an in-depth understanding of the participants, the first two questions in the questionnaire are designed to determine the number of years the subjects have studied English as well as the language skill they spent most of the time learning at high school. The results show that nearly 70% of the participants have studied English for 7 years or more. Moreover, when they studied English at high school, 80% of studying time was spent on Reading and Writing skill, while Speaking and Listening skill accounted for only 20% of studying time.

3.2 Research design

In the light of the nature of the research questions, the study was carried out with quantitative and qualitative methods of data collection. The quantitative method is a questionnaire survey with 150 first-year English major students at HUFU. The qualitative method is a focus-group interview with subjects to enrich the quantitative data.

3.3 Instruments

The instruments used in this study are a questionnaire and a focus-group interview with the subjects. These instruments are described in detail below.

The first instrument which is employed in this study is a questionnaire. The questionnaire is used to get information about the perception of students of the role of listening comprehension skills as well as of the difficulties the students face when studying EFL listening at HUFU. The questionnaire is designed after a review of literature about the factors affecting listening comprehension (Boyle, 1984; Underwood, 1989; Hamouda, 2013).

The questionnaire consists of two sections. Section one contains 5 questions used to collect the students' learning experience, their perception of the importance of listening skill and their self-evaluated English listening proficiency level. Section 2 includes 35 questions grouped into 6 categories: Listening materials (6 items), linguistic characteristics (6 items), speakers (6 items), listener (9 items), lack of concentration (4 items) and physical setting (4 items). The questionnaire uses the Likert-type scale from 1 to 5. Individual items in Likert's sample scale have five response alternatives: Never, Rarely, Sometimes, Usually, and Always. The subjects are asked to indicate how often they meet the problem by choosing from 1 to 5.

The second instrument employed in this study is focus-group interview with 30 students. The participants are formed into groups of six to provide in-depth information about their difficulties in learning listening comprehension.

3.4 Data analysis

The data collected through the questionnaire and the interview is organized and analyzed using the soft-ware SPSS. The questionnaires are computed for means, modes, medians and standard deviation (SD) in order to reveal the problems in listening comprehension perceived by EFL learners at HUFU. The criteria for judging the degree of the problems are shown in the following table.

Table 1: Criteria for judging the degree of problems

Degree of problems	Mean
Very high	4.21-5.00
High	3.41-4.20
Moderate	2.61-3.40
Low	1.81-2.60
Very low	1.00-1.80

The respondents' opinions and suggestions collected through interviews are analyzed by using content analysis.

4 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Students' perceived importance of English listening comprehension

Table 2: Students' perceived importance of English listening comprehension

Item	Mean	Mode	Median	SD	Meaning
Students' perceived importance of English listening comprehension	4.67	5	5	0.66	Very high

As illustrated in Table 2, the total mean of this cluster (4.67) is much higher than the average of Likert-type scale rating from 1 – Not important at all to 5 – Extremely important. In addition, the mode and median are equal (5). These statistics show that most of the participants have a very positive perception of the listening role in English language learning.

The content analysis of the interviews also demonstrates that the majority of the first-year English major students at HUFU are aware of the importance of the English listening comprehension. Most of the interviewees appreciate the role of listening skills in the development of communication skills. They hope that their increased listening proficiency will help them to be more confident in communicating with foreigners. In addition, they state that listening can complement their pronunciation and widen their vocabulary resource. However, most of the interviewed students consider listening the most challenging skill to acquire. In fact nearly 90% of them indicate that listening is extremely difficult.

4.2 Students' perceived factors affecting English listening comprehension

Table 3: Descriptive analysis of factors affecting listening comprehension as perceived by the students

Item	Mean	Mode	Median	SD	Meaning
Factors related to listening texts	3.81	4	4	0.87	High
Factors related to linguistic features	3.82	4	4	0.92	High
Factors related to the speaker	3.74	4	4	1.03	High
Factors related to the listener	3.73	4	4	0.97	High
Factors related to the failure to concentrate	3.66	4	4	0.93	High
Factors related to physical setting	3.44	3	3	0.93	High
Total	3.72	4	4	0.95	High

Figure 1: Factors affecting listening comprehension

It is noticeable from the Table 3 that the total mean score of all the factors considered in this study is 3.72 (SD = 0.95), which is higher than the average, and the mode and the median are the same (=4). These reveal that most of the participants perceive all mentioned items as factors which cause problems in their listening comprehension. In addition, the standard deviations, showing the dispersion of data, are not high, rating from 0.87 to 1.03, which means that the opinions of the respondents about the factors affecting their listening comprehension are relatively concentrated and homogeneous.

Among all the listening problem factors surveyed, the factors related to linguistic features of the listening materials have the highest mean score (3.82), followed closely by the problems related to listening texts (3.81). The mean scores of the factors related to speakers and listeners are nearly the same at 3.74 and 3.73 respectively. The mean score of the difficulties arising from listeners' failure to concentrate stand at 3.66, and the lowest mean score is of the factors related to physical setting (3.44).

4.2.1 Factors related to listening texts

Table 4: Factors related to listening texts

Items	Mean	Mode	Median	SD	Meaning
Q6. I find it difficult to understand listening texts which have too many unfamiliar words.	4.15	4	4	0.77	High
Q7. Difficult grammar structures interfere with my listening comprehension.	3.91	4	4	0.88	High
Q8. I find it difficult to understand listening texts when the topic is unfamiliar.	3.65	3	4	0.83	High

Items	Mean	Mode	Median	SD	Meaning
Q9. I find it difficult to interpret the meaning of a long listening text.	3.75	4	4	0.96	High
Q10. I use my experience and background knowledge of the topic to understand the spoken text.	3.65	4	4	0.85	High
Q11. I find the listening passage difficult to understand.	3.73	3	4	0.80	High
Total	3.81	4	4	0.87	High

As presented in Table 4, the problems related to listening texts are all at high levels (Mean = 3.81). The participants respond that limited English vocabulary interferes most with their listening comprehension (Mean = 4.15), followed by the difficulty of grammatical structures (3.91), the length of the spoken texts (3.75), the difficulty of the material (3.73), the unfamiliarity of the topic and the use of basic background knowledge (3.65).

During the focus-group interviews, many respondents confirm that lack of words is the major factor that hinders their listening comprehension. Take the interviewee 4 as example,

“My vocabulary source is poor, so it’s very difficult for me to understand the content of the spoken text if the text contains lots of new words.”

A great number of the interviewees also complain that sometimes the recording texts are so long and difficult with unfamiliar topics that they cannot concentrate on listening to understand and answer the questions. As Interviewee 23 shares,

“There are some topics in the textbook that I have no idea about. In addition, some of the recording are so lengthy. In fact I think I can’t listen continuously for more than 3 minutes.”

Some respondents also mention the problem related to the complexity of grammatical structures.

In short, the results of the questionnaires and the interviews indicate that listening text itself is the main source of listening comprehension difficulties. In particular, unfamiliar words, complex grammatical structures, lengthy spoken texts with unfamiliar topics impede the learners’ listening comprehension.

4.2.2 Factors related to linguistic features

Table 5: Factors related to linguistic features

Items	Mean	Mode	Median	SD	Meaning
Q12. I find the pronunciation familiar but cannot recognize the word.	3.95	4	4	0.80	High
Q13. I find it difficult to understand when the speakers use reduced forms of words such as gotcha, kinda.	4.03	4	4	0.86	High
Q14. I find it difficult to recognize the signals which indicate that the speaker is moving from one point to another.	3.78	4	4	0.90	High
Q15. When encountering an unknown word, I stop listening and think about the meaning of the word.	3.44	4	4	1.00	High
Q16. Slang and idiomatic expressions interfere with my listening comprehension.	3.96	4	4	0.95	High
Q17. I find it difficult to follow the sequence of the spoken text if the sentences are too long and complex.	3.76	4	4	0.85	High
Total	3.82	4	4	0.92	High

As shown in Table 5, linguistic features of the English language are the factors that cause more difficulty for first-year English major students at HUFU than any other ones. Among those factors, the biggest problem is the use of reduced form (4.03), followed closely by the use of slang and idiomatic expressions in the spoken text (3.96) and the mismatch between the pronunciation and the spelling of English words (3.95). In addition, long and complex sentences as well as the failure to recognize discourse markers that speakers use in the spoken text also result in a high level of problems in listening comprehension for the respondents, at Mean = 3.76 and 3.78 respectively.

The result of the interviews provides some insight into the causes of these problems. Many interviewees confirm that in classrooms, they are usually exposed to the full and formal forms of the English language. Their teachers as well as their classmates usually pronounce words separately and clearly and their intonation seem to be flat. That is the reason why when they listen to natural spoken English in which people frequently use reduced forms as well as colloquial words and expressions, they find it difficult to understand.

4.2.3 Factors related to the speakers

Table 6: Factors related to the speakers

Items	Mean	Mode	Median	SD	Meaning
Q18. I find it difficult to understand the meaning of the words which are not pronounced clearly.	4.02	4	4	0.87	High
Q19. I find it difficult to understand the natural speech which is full of hesitation and pauses.	3.61	4	4	1.04	High
Q20. I find it difficult to understand well when speakers speak too fast.	4.17	5	4	0.94	High
Q21. I find it difficult to understand when speakers use various accents.	3.48	4	4	1.02	High
Q22. I find it difficult to understand the listening text when the speaker does not pause long enough.	3.23	3	3	1.00	Moderate
Q23. I find it difficult to understand the recorded material if I am unable to get things repeated.	3.95	4	4	0.85	High
Total	3.74	4	4	1.03	High

It is noticeable from Table 6 that factors related to the speakers in the recording are rated at a high level (Mean=3.74). According to the respondents, the fast rate of speech is the number one factor obstructing their listening comprehension. In fact, all the participants state that they have difficulty in understanding the spoken texts in which the speakers speak fast (Mode = 5). In addition to speed of delivery, unclear pronunciation of the speakers and the inability to get things repeated are considered great sources of listening comprehension problems. The questionnaire results show that more than 80% of the participants cannot comprehend the listening text as a result of unclear pronunciation and their only one exposure to the recording. The speakers' use of various accents in natural dialogues with lots of hesitation and pauses also impede the participants' listening comprehension at the mean of 3.48 and 3.61 respectively. Lack of pauses, however, is considered the least challenging among the factors related to speakers.

During the interviews, a common view shared by the majority of respondents is that the high speed of delivery hinders their ability to understand the recording. Interviewee 30 says,

“The rate of speech is too fast for me to catch up with. Usually I can only listen to 50% of the recording and only after the teacher explains can I understand the text. What’s more, I usually cannot understand the text just after the first listening.”

They also say that in classrooms, they are familiar with their teacher’s speed which is often slower than the recording; therefore, they even feel shocked when the speakers in the recording speak too fast.

Many interviewees state that they are familiar neither with the accents nor with the pronunciation of the speakers in the recording because they are quite different from what they know and learn from their teachers. Their teachers do not use intonation or stress on words or sentences much. Some students even blame their teachers at high school for their incorrect pronunciation. From these opinions, it can be inferred that sometimes speakers’ pronunciation is not the main cause of listening difficulties, but the obstacles come from the listeners themselves whose pronunciations are not good enough to understand varied types of accents.

In short, listening comprehension problems can be related to speaking in terms of fast rate of delivery, natural speech, pronunciation, various accents and a voice heard only one time.

4.2.4 Factors related to listeners

Table 7: Factors related to the listener

Items	Mean	Mode	Median	SD	Meaning
Q24: I find it difficult to get a general understanding of the spoken text from the first time of listening.	4.09	5	4	0.81	High
Q25. At the time of listening, I find it difficult to predict what will come next.	3.91	5	4	0.95	High
Q26. I find it difficult to quickly remember words or phrases I have just heard.	3.5	3	3	0.94	High
Q27. I find it difficult when listening to English without transcripts.	3.76	4	4	0.95	High
Q28. Lack of listening strategies and listening skill training interferes with my listening comprehension.	4.03	5	4	0.94	High
Q29. I find it difficult to answer questions which require other than short answer.	3.93	4	4	0.80	High
Q30. I find it difficult to understand the spoken text which is of no interest to me.	3.53	3	3	0.96	High

Items	Mean	Mode	Median	SD	Meaning
Q31. I feel nervous and worried when I don't understand the spoken text.	3.80	5	4	1.03	High
Q32. I stop listening when I have problems in understanding a listening text.	3.05	4	3	0.91	Moderate
Total	3.73	4	4	0.97	High

As presented in Table 7, the listener's inability to get a general idea from the first listening and to predict what will come next has the highest mean scores, at 4.09 and 3.91 respectively. Lack of listening strategies and difficult question types have high mean scores (4.03 and 3.93). The factors related to the psychological characteristics of the listener such as anxiety and lack of interest and motivation are also rated at relatively high levels (3.80 and 3.53).

The interviews with the participants reveal that lack of listening strategies is the main source of listening comprehension problems related to listeners. Almost all of the interviewees state that they were not taught listening strategies when they studied at high school. As a result, they do not know what to do before listening and while listening in order to get the correct answers. Some of them even do not know the concept of "keyword" or what types of words in the recording could be categorized as "keywords". This is also the reason why they find difficult to predict what will come next in the recording and to answer questions which require other than short answers.

A considerable number of the interviewees confess that they do not like listening and they find some of the listening texts boring and of no interest to them; therefore, they do not pay attention to listening in classrooms. Many respondents admit that they do not often practise listening outside classrooms. In fact for some students the only time they practise listening is in class. Some other interviewees share that they are aware of the important role of listening skills but their listening proficiency is so low that they usually feel nervous and lose confidence when they cannot catch the words or understand the recording.

In short, it can be inferred from the results of the questionnaires and the interviews that the problems in listening comprehension may arise from the listeners themselves, especially their inability to understand the spoken text from the first listening, their anxiety, their lack of interest in the listening texts as well as their lack of listening strategies.

4.2.5 Factors related the failure to concentrate

Table 8: Factors related to the failure to concentrate

Items	Mean	Mode	Median	SD	Meaning
Q33. I lose concentration when I think of another question.	3.24	4	3	0.83	Moderate
Q34. I lose concentration when the text is too long.	3.83	4	4	0.86	High
Q35. I lose concentration when I think about the meaning of new words.	3.98	5	4	0.95	High
Q36. I am unable to concentrate because I search for the answers and listen to the listening text at the same time.	3.62	3	4	0.90	High
Total	3.67	4	4	0.93	High

Table 8 reveals that the failure to concentrate affects the participants' ability to understand the spoken texts. New words, the length of the spoken text, the activity of searching for the answer at the same time as listening as well as thinking about another question all lead to the focus loss.

Among the factors mentioned above, the respondents tend to be most distracted by the new words (Mean = 3.98) and then fail to keep focus on useful clues in the context. Text length is also responded as a major cause of concentration failure. Many participants (Mean = 3.83) state that it is difficult for them to concentrate if the text is long.

The results of the interviews seem to be relevant to the results of the questionnaires. Many interviewed students acknowledge that whenever they meet a new word or phrase in the recording, they will try to find out its meaning; hence, they lose their focus on the content of the recording. In addition, a significant number of interviewees state that they cannot concentrate on the listening text if they have to listen and search for the answer at the same time especially when the spoken text is too long.

4.2.6 Factors related to the physical settings

Table 9: Factors related to the physical setting

Items	Mean	Mode	Median	SD	Meaning
Q37: Unclear sounds resulting from poor classroom conditions interfere with my listening comprehension.	3.79	3	4	0.91	High

Items	Mean	Mode	Median	SD	Meaning
Q38. Unclear sounds resulting from poor - quality equipment such as CD - players interfere with my listening comprehension.	2.90	3	3	0.72	Moderate
Q39. Lack of visual clues (picture, diagrams, videos, etc) interferes with my listening comprehension.	3.02	3	3	0.70	Moderate
Q40. It is difficult for me to listen with noises around.	4.08	5	4	0.81	High
Total	3.44	3	3	0.93	High

As illustrated in Table 9, in general, factors related to physical setting are rated rather higher than the accepted mean score. The respondents' highest mean score regarding physical setting factors is 4.08 while the lowest one is 2.90.

The results reveal that the noise both outside and inside classrooms is a main obstacle to listening comprehension, at the mean score of 4.08 and 3.79 respectively whereas the poor quality of CD players and lack of visual support are reported by the participants as sometimes impeding their listening comprehension.

During the interviews, all the participants blame the exterior noise especially the sound of airplanes for interfering their listening comprehension. They explain more that all the classrooms at HUFU are not sound-insulated, so usually while they are focusing on listening, the sudden noise of airplanes disturbs them and as a result, they fail to concentrate on the listening. Moreover, large class is referred by many students as a hindrance to their listening comprehension. As Interviewee 15 shares,

“There are over 60 students in my class. I think that’s too large for a foreign language class. My teacher can’t pay enough attention to each student in class. Moreover, during listening sessions, they are usually noisy so I can’t hear anything.”

Some of the interviewees state their teacher rarely use visual clues such as videos, diagrams or pictures during the listening sessions and this interferes with their listening comprehension. They suggest that teachers should use more visual teaching aids to make it easier for them to learn new words as well as to understand the spoken texts.

In conclusion, the results of the questionnaires and the focus-group interviews with the subjects reveal that the majority of first-year English major students at HUFU well perceive the importance of listening comprehension. However, most of them do have difficulties understanding the listening texts. Among the factors affecting the students' listening comprehension, the fast rate of speech is considered the number one problem, followed closely by the listeners' limited

vocabulary including slang and colloquial expressions and noise both inside and outside the classrooms. The listeners' poor pronunciation and lack of exposure to various aspects of natural speech such as reduced forms, intonations, pauses and hesitation also cause a lot of problems in listening comprehension for the participants. Their listening comprehension hindrances, moreover, arise from their lack of listening strategies as well as control over the listening materials they learn in classrooms and their limited time of practising listening outside classrooms.

4.3 Implications

Based on the findings, the research would like to propose some suggestions for teachers as well as students at Faculty of Foreign Languages, HUFI in order to deal with the listening comprehension problems.

Firstly, physical setting of listening including listening laboratory, CDs, CD-players and classrooms is an important factor that affects the quality of both learning and teaching listening skill. However, according to the participants of this study, the current learning environment at HUFI is still unsatisfactory with noisy classrooms and no listening laboratory. It is, thus, vital for the university to invest more in classrooms as well as in multimedia laboratories so that all the students, especially English major ones, have more chances to learn and practise listening skills.

Secondly, the findings of this study indicate that the listening materials that are being used at HUFI are quite challenging and not of interest of many students. Therefore, it is recommended that teachers should adapt these materials to match a variety of interests, learning styles and abilities of their students. In particular, it is advisable that for first-year students, at first teachers should choose the recordings with slower speed of speech and then they can increase the level of difficulties when the students are more proficient.

Thirdly, it is inferred from this study that insufficient vocabulary is one of the main causes of listening comprehension problems among first-year English major students at HUFI. It is, therefore, important that before listening, teachers equip students with key words related to the topic in the recording. There are many ways to do this, but it is better to activate students' vocabulary sources by asking them to guess the meaning of new words which are used in the listening context (Hamouda, 2013). In addition, teachers should also activate students' background knowledge of the content of the listening text before listening. Teachers can encourage their students to discuss what they already know about the topic they are going to listen as well as to predict what they might hear in the listening text so that the students become more familiar with the topic before listening.

Fourthly, from the investigation, it is clear that the majority of English major freshmen at HUFI lack listening strategies and listening skill training so they usually have difficulties doing listening comprehension tasks. It is suggested that more time should be allotted to train students with tactics and techniques for listening before requiring them to practise in class.

Finally, the English linguistic knowledge which includes pronunciation, connected speech, accents, discourse markers, slang and idiomatic expressions, and grammatical structures is

concluded from this study as the number one cause of problems in listening comprehension. Therefore, it is necessary for students to be exposed more to authentic English by listening to native voices through English songs, English news, films, plays, daily conversation or stories which are suitable for their levels. In addition, teachers should equip their students with linguistic features such as transition languages, colloquial expressions or grammatical structures at convenient time during the listening sessions.

5 CONCLUSION

This study attempts to investigate the perceptions of first-year English major students at HUFU of the English listening comprehension role in the process of language learning as well as the factors that affect their listening comprehension. The findings indicate that the students are well aware of the importance of listening comprehension while they consider it the most challenging language skill to acquire. Therefore, the English major freshmen at HUFU have a lot of listening comprehension problems which are related to English linguistic features, listening materials, the speaker, the listener, and the learning environment at HUFU. Among the surveyed factors, the main causes of problems are speaker's fast rate of speech, listener's limited knowledge of English linguistic features such as pronunciation, contractions, accents and discourse markers, listener's lack of listening strategies and concentration, and the effect of noisy classrooms resulted from badly-equipped classrooms.

REFERENCES

- [1] Anderson, A. & Lynch, T. (1998). *Listening*. Oxford University Press.
- [2] Boyle, J.P. (1984). Factors affecting listening comprehension. *ELT Journal*, 38(1), 34-38. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/elt/38.134>
- [3] Brown, G. & Yule, G. (1983). *Teaching the spoken language*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- [4] Coakley, C. & Wolin, A. (1986). Listening in the native language. In B.H. Wing (Ed.), *Listening, reading, and writing: Analysis and application* (pp. 11-42). Middlebury: Northeast Conference on the teaching of foreign languages.
- [5] Dirven, R., & Oakeshott-Taylor, J. (1984). Listening comprehension (Part I). *Language Teaching: The International Abstracting Journal for Language Teachers and Applied Linguistics*, 17 (4), 326-334. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/S026144480001082X>
- [6] Goh, C. (2000). A cognitive perspective on language learners' listening comprehension problems. *System*, 28, pp. 55-75.
- [7] Hamouda, A. (2013). An investigation of listening comprehension problems encountered by Saudi Students in the EL Listening classroom. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 2(2), 113-155.
- [8] Howatt, A. & Dakin, J. (1974). Language laboratory materials . In J.P.B. Allen, S.P.B. Allen & S.P. Corder (Eds). New York, USA: McGraw-Hill, pp. 43-70

- [9] Krashen, S.D. (1985). *The input hypothesis*. London, England: Longman.
- [10] Mendelson, D.J. (1994). *Learning to listen: A strategy-based approach for the second language learner*. San Diego: Dominie Press.
- [11] Mendelson, D.J & Rubin, J. (1995). *A guide for the teaching of second language listening*. California, USA: Dominie Press
- [12] Nadig, A. (2013). Listening comprehension. *Encyclopedia of autism spectrum disorders*, 1753.
- [13] Nunan, D. (1997). Approaches to teaching listening in the language classroom. In *Proceedings of the 1997 Korea TESOL conference*. Taejion, Korea: KOTESOL.
- [14] Oxford, R.L. (1990). *Language learning strategies: What every teacher should know*. New York, USA: Newbury House.
- [15] Quyen, N.N & Dan, T.C. (2018). Listening comprehension: First-year English major students' perceptions and problems. *Can Tho Journal of science*, 54(2), 75-83.
- [16] Richards, J.C., Plat, J. & Platt, H. (2000). *Longman Dictionary of Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics*. Beijing, China: Foreign Language Teaching and Research Press.
- [17] Rost, M. (2002). *Teaching and Researching Listening*. London, England: Longman.
- [18] Rubin, J. (1994). A review of second language listening comprehension research. *Modern language journal*, 78 (2), 199-221. Retrieved from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/329010>
- [19] Teng, H.C. (2002). An investigation of EFL listening difficulties for Taiwanese college students. *Selected papers from the Eleventh international symposium on English teaching/Fourth Pan-Asian Conference*, pp. 526-533.
- [20] Underwood, M. (1989). *Teaching listening*. Harlow, England: Longman, p.981.
- [21] Wilt, M. E. (1950). A study of teacher awareness of listening as a factor in elementary education. *Journal of Educational Research*, 43 (8), 626- 636.